

USER PREFERENCE ON MOBILE APPLICATIONS AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Mobile has become an integral part of every individual of this generation. It has also been considered as a basic need of everyone. Usage of Mobile applications equally plays a vital role among the users of various mobile models available in the market. Mobile Applications in the earlier days were originally offered for general productivity and information retrieval, including E-mail, drive calendar, contacts, stock market and whether information. But the service of mobile applications now-a-days has been widening to a larger extent and hence the objective of the present study is based on the Preference and Problems of Mobile Applications users. Questionnaire Method is used to collect the data for this research. 110 respondents were taken for the study using convenient sampling technique. For analyzing the data the Simple Percentage and Weighted Average Method is applied. The major findings of the study and suitable suggestions are presented in this article.

Key Words: Mobile, Applications & College Students

Introduction:

A Mobile Application is a software application designed to run on mobile devices. Most of the mobile devices are sold out with several applications bundled as pre-installed software, such as a web browser, Email Client, Calendar, Mapping program, an application for music or other media and so on based on the model of the device that is being purchased. Applications that are not pre-installed are usually available through distribution platforms called App Store. They began appearing in 2008 and are typically operated by the owner of the Mobile Operating System, such as the Apple App Store, Google Play Store, Windows Phone Store, and Black Berry App World. The term "APP" is the short form of the term "Application" Software. The Mobile Apps in the earlier days were originally offered for general productivity and information retrieval, including E-mail, drive calendar, contacts, stock Market and whether information. An analyst in the report estimated that the app economy has generated revenues for more than 10 billion euro per year among the European country which has stated clearly the growth of the app market. Considering the current market trends online business like Web hosting, Shopping, Job portals, etc have developed Mobile Applications for their clients to provide better services. Each applications developed by various owners of the apps, offer their customers with competing services to make them hold among their app usage and to widen their market.

Scope of the Study:

The usage of Mobile phones simultaneously increased the usage of mobile applications in the recent days. India stands second in the world in the number of active mobile phones as per the last research conducted in the year 2011. With the increase in the number of Mobile phones, there comes automatically a demand for Mobile Applications as there is a high switch over among the users from the basic model of mobile phones to various advanced versions of operating systems in their mobile models. This research study hence extends its scope in helping to identify the user preference and problems faced in usage of Mobile Applications among college students. It helps to know about the user frequency and choice of applications. This study also helps to examine in identifying which age group of respondents prefer in using the mobile applications at greater level and also helps to know the negative impacts of smart phone applications among the users.

Statement of the Problem:

India stands second in the use of Mobile phones. Mobile Application usage has increased tremendously. So it's important to know the preferences of Applications by the users. Mobile Application denotes the process of application software for mobile devices. Mobile applications have been steadily growing, in revenues and job creation. A mobile app needs to be made suit each platform of devices as, android, windows etc., and the Mobile Application vulnerabilities exist because inexperienced program have bad data storage. It may cause the malware effect to the device. Mobile applications are not as simple to optimize as mobile websites. Considering these problems, the present study focus on the questions of whether the users of mobile applications face any issues in it and whether it is secured (or) whether they face any privacy related problems and whether they come over any negative impacts while using the Mobile Applications.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To study the preferences of users on Mobile Applications.
- ✓ To evaluate the problem faced by the users of Mobile Applications.

Methodology:

The data required for study have been collected through questionnaire. Questions relating to the Personal Profile, Preference and Problems of users towards Mobile Applications are included in the questionnaire.

Sample Size and Data Collection:

The study is concerned with users of Mobile Applications. About 120 users of Mobile Applications in Pollachi town are included in the samples out of which 110 respondents' questionnaire which are completed fully are taken for the analysis. Convenience sampling method has been followed to choose the sample. The secondary data is collected from journals and internet and the collected information are incorporated as follows:

- ✓ Review of literature
- ✓ Mobile Applications factors.

Statistical Tool Applied:

The statistical tools used for this study is Simple Percentage and Weighted Average Ranking.

Limitations of the Study:

The drawbacks of the study are:

- ✓ The area of the study is limited to pollachi only.
- ✓ The data provided by the respondents may be biased due to the confidential nature of the information sort.
- ✓ The data collected for the present is constrained to the college students only and so the preferences of other group of people are not taken for the consideration of the analysis.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Device Wise Classification

Device Platform	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Android	89	81
Iphone	8	7
Windows	9	8
Black Berry	4	4
Total	110	100

From the table 1, it is observed that out of 110 respondents 89(81%) respondents are using Android, 8(7%) respondents are using iphone, 9(8%) respondents are using windows and 4(4%) respondent are using Black Berry.

Hence the study reveals that most of the respondents 89(81%) are owing the Android platform as their mobile device.

Table 2: Preference Wise Classification

Preference	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Top Free	54	49
Top Paid	16	15
Top Grossing	3	2
Top new paid	5	4
Top new free	16	15
Trending	16	15
Total	110	100

From the above table 2, it is observed that out of 110 respondents 54(49%) respondents prefer to download Top free applications, 16(15%) respondents download Top paid, followed by 3(2%) respondents Top Grossing, 5(4%) respondents prefer Top new paid, 16(15%) respondents download Top new free, 16(15%) respondents prefer to download Trending kind of applications.

Hence the study reveals that the majority of respondents 54(49%) prefer to download Top free applications.

Table 3: Factor Wise Classification

Factors	Total	Rank
Reviews	235	I
Ratings	275	II
Description	280	III
Free Trial	310	IV

The above table 3 specifies the factors which make the users to download an application and out of 110 respondents, the first rank has been given for the factor "Reviews", second rank for "Ratings", followed by

“Description” and the last rank is given for “Free Trial”. Hence it is found that, the majority of the respondents has given the first rank for the factor “Review” showing their highest preference for it.

Table 4: Level of Agreement

Factors	SA (%)	A (%)	N (%)	DA (%)	SDA (%)
Loss interest owing to advertisement	49	32	12	3	4
Use mobile applications using internet	35	25	23	10	7
Ready to pay for mobile applications	10	29	31	14	16
Use mobile applications frequently	48	31	18	2	1
Found unnecessary complexity	22	28	26	16	8
Frequently download applications	29	27	33	8	3
Mobile application are well integrated	24	35	27	10	4
Factors	SA (%)	A (%)	N(%)	DA(%)	SDA (%)
Easy to use	38	35	19	4	4
Need to learn a lot about applications	26	34	24	10	6
Usage behavior is consistent experience	20	38	30	6	6

From the above table 4, it is clearly specified that the users’ level of agreement on mobile application. Out of 110 respondents, 49% of the respondents strongly agree that they loss interest owing to advertisement, 35% of the respondents agree that they prefer to use mobile applications more when using internet (or) wifi, 31% of the respondents are neutral with that of the point that they are ready to pay for mobile applications and 48% of the respondents says that they strongly agree that they use mobile applications frequently, 28% of the respondents agree that they found unnecessary complexity in using mobile applications, 33% of the respondents are neutral with that they frequently download applications. 35% of the respondents agree that the function of mobile application are well integrated, 38% of the respondents strongly agree that the applications are easy to use, 34% of the respondents agree that before using an application, they need to learn a lot, 38% of the respondents agree that the application usage behavior is a consistent experience.

Table 5: Impact Wise Classification

Impacts	Total	Rank
Privacy related problem	313	I
Health related problems	348	V
Thinking capacity decrease	328	III
Reduce communication with family	338	IV
High Internet Cost	323	II

The above table 5 specifies the impacts of the respondents they come over in usage of device applications. Out of 110 respondents, the first rank is attained by the impact “Privacy related problem”, second by “High internet cost”, followed by “Thinking capacity decrease” as third, Reduce communication with family” as of fourth and the last rank is given for “Health related problems”.

Summary of Findings:

- ✓ Majority (81%) of the respondents owe the Android platform.
- ✓ Majority (49 %) of the respondents Level of Agreement says that they strongly agree that they loss interest owing to advertisement.
- ✓ Majority (49%) of the respondents prefer to download Top free applications.
- ✓ Highest ranking is attained for the factor “Reviews” which makes them to decide in downloading choice of an application.
- ✓ Top rank has also been attained in the impact analysis for the “Privacy related problem” by the user over come in their device.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Downloading an application in any link (or) websites may lead to virus threats and may affect the mobile devices as the users are without the knowledge of reaching the right way of downloading and hence the users should be given awareness on the valid applications that are to be downloaded from their mobile stores.
- ✓ Sometimes update of an application affect the normal functioning of the same as of before its updation and so the functioning of an application should be checked before it has be let out for the users which helps in continuing as well as increasing the number of users for an application.
- ✓ While using an application some Ads pop up and sending of Junk files by the developers may be avoided or reduced to increase the app users.
- ✓ Some applications observe a lot of battery consumption and drain the device battery. Such applications may be considered and developed in such a way of less battery consumption so that it may help the users to handle with such applications which may be on the other side an interesting app of the users.

- ✓ An application developed shall not occupy a wider amount of memory space so that the users might be interested in using such applications that are compact in nature.
- ✓ Applications should be in the platform that copes with speed and relevance of data.
- ✓ Security breach is that password issues, the data's synced to the application are getting hacked. An app's security is deeply impacted by the under lying device's security.
- ✓ An app should be User – Friendly simple and innovative. It should satisfy the end user.
- ✓ Occasionally, the mobile apps don't work properly, extremely slow and get crashed and hence the developers should try to take care of such issues.
- ✓ Applications Personalization shall be provided as it is being loved by everyone in changing the settings, fonts, colors and so on, so that the users can make the app look the way they want it.

Conclusion:

Mobile application is a software application developed specifically for use on small wireless computing devices such as Smart phones. Mobile apps are designed with constraints of the devices capabilities they have. Mobile apps can come preloaded on the hand held device as well as can be downloaded by users from app stores or the internet. A mobile application may be known to be as an app, web app, online app, and smart app. This study focus its attempt on knowing the socio economic profile of the respondents such as Gender, Age, Area, Marital Status, Educational Qualification, Type of Family, No of Earning Members, Monthly Income and the User Preference of Mobile Application Platform and Factors issuing in Mobile Application Usage and Impacts of Mobile Applications helping the application developers to be cautious in developing the applications based on the findings interpreted from the present study.

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